

EXPRESSION OF LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC FEATURES IN THE TRANSLATIONS OF THE NOVEL BY PIRIMKUL KADYROV

Ochilova Nafisa Usmonovna

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6303260>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th February 2022

Accepted: 20th February 2022

Online: 25th February 2022

KEY WORDS

*translation, fiction novel,
expression, stylistic
translation, feature*

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to determine the features of the expression of linguistic and stylistic features in translations of P. Kadyrov's novel "Beaver" in the English-Russian language pair. The peculiarities of the use of stylistic devices in translation activity, it is necessary, first of all, to refer to the basic concepts of translation and translation activity.

One of the most common types of translation in the modern world is literary translation. Literary translation is the translation of fiction.

Such literary works are special because their main purpose is the interest of readers. The main function is communicative, namely artistic and aesthetic or poetic. Literary works of this direction put their main focus on the achievement of figurativeness. This effect cannot be achieved without active work on the use of stylistic devices in translation.

P. Kadyrov noted that the brighter and more colorful the image of a literary character is, the greater the impact it will have on the reader. This effect can be achieved by giving it imagery on the principle of adding stylistic means of expression. That is why the issue of preserving such imagery and the author's style is extremely important in the translation of fiction. This style of

translation requires a careful selection of artistic language means.

Speaking about the special style of works of art, it is necessary to remember the fact that it is associated with emotionality and expressiveness, metaphor, meaningful versatility of the artistic style of speech. As an example, we tied P. Kadyrov's novel.

In the novel "Starry Nights" P. Kadyrov brought out an impressive image of Zakhiriddin Babur (late 15th - early 16th century), who not only ruled a huge power that included Transoxiana and India, but was also one of the most enlightened people of his time. The writer showed feudal fragmentation, strife among the ruling elite, increased tax burden, devastation - the characteristic features of that era, in the atmosphere of which Babur was formed as a poet, historian and statesman. The novel vividly depicts pictures of civil strife in Ferghana,

Samarkand, shows the role of the masses, their attitude towards wars and oppressors. In the translation of fiction, various stylistic devices and tropes are used. Their use depends on the desire of the author and / or translator to achieve the goal. Among them, the most common are the speech polysemy of the word, which reveals meanings and semantic shades in it, as well as synonymy at all language levels, which makes it possible to emphasize the subtlest shades of meanings. This is explained by the fact that the author strives to use all the richness of the language, to create his own unique language and style, to a bright, expressive, figurative text. The author uses not only the vocabulary of the codified literary language, but also a variety of figurative means from colloquial speech and vernacular. A special place is played by phrases that create a figurative representation that creates an emotional mood.

The most significant distinguishing feature of the literary translation of the novel is the extremely active use of Beaubourg's tropes and figures of speech. This property of texts of artistic functional style was noticed quite a long time ago. In the process of carrying out the work, the translator carrying out the language transformation faces the difficult task of preserving a large number of tropes and figures of speech as an important component of the artistic style of a work.

When working on the analysis of the stylistic features of translation, it is also necessary to pay attention to such a linguistic phenomenon as stylistic transformation. This term is commonly understood as the transformation of the style of the text in the transfer of stylistic

meaning in order to recreate the same effect in translation, i.e. evoke a similar reaction in the reader, although often the translator has to achieve this by resorting to completely different linguistic means, using substitution and compensation techniques. It is one of the most complex ways of translation transformations. It is also necessary to create a special atmosphere in a literary work.

In the analyzed novel, it was noted that the preservation of the stylistic translation of the originality of the source text should be carried out taking into account the functional or pragmatic factor. Taking into account this information, it becomes possible to assert that the goal of the person performing the translation is to achieve the maximum correspondence of the translation version to the version of the original text, including the transfer of all stylistic features of the original. As a result, the reader who reads the translation version should see a text similar to the original source. However, if the translator failed to convey a lively, emotional image of the original or replaced a specific image with a more complex, more abstract one, the translation will not correspond to the original.

It should be noted that the emotionality of artistic narration is very different from the emotionality of colloquial and journalistic styles. In a literary text, it performs an aesthetic function. This style involves a careful and reasonable selection of language means. A distinctive feature of a literary text is the use of special figures of speech that add brightness and imagery to the narrative.

Continuing to talk about the role of translation in the modern world, one cannot remain silent about global

advertising, since along with text advertisements, there are also such types of advertising that, being standard for the whole world, use generally recognized phrases or stereotypes to support the feeling associated with the peculiarity of the advertised product. In addition, to facilitate the perception of a foreign language, there are pictograms that can also be classified as advertising texts, since they carry certain information with them. Pictograms can also be the subject of special study, since they often visually complement the advertising text and often help the translator find the necessary language tools.

To attract attention, advertising sometimes uses the text of a foreign

language. The use of words from another language violates the grammatical norms of the reader, and therefore attracts attention and becomes part of the "visual design" along with color and image. But a foreign text can also cause a breakdown in communication if the words are incomprehensible, in which case the translator's task is to use all knowledge of the theoretical foundations of translation to transfer the communicative function of the original.

Knowledge of the theoretical foundations of translation and extralinguistic realities is a necessary condition for the adequacy of translation.

REFERENCES:

1. Звездные ночи Пиримкул Кадыров 1981 Издательство: Известия
[Phttps://www.livelib.ru/author/227957/top-pirimkul-kadyrov](https://www.livelib.ru/author/227957/top-pirimkul-kadyrov)
2. Khakimova M. F., Mirzaeva M. N., Bazarova U. M., Musakhanova G. M. Opportunities of innovation technologies in higher education. International Journal on Integrated Education. 3, 12 (Dec. 2020), 282-285. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v3i12.1002>.
3. U. Bazarova, S. Suyarova Development formation of professional competence and moral education system for students of universities// Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka, 2021
4. Bazarova U.M. The Role of Spiritual and Moral Education of Students of Technical University in the Lessons of Foreign Languages. // Philadelphia, USA-2019.-614-616s.
5. Bazarova U.M. The state of the problem of moral and aesthetic education of students by means of a foreign language at the present stage // International scientific journal "Scientific Horizons" No. 1 / Moscow 2019
6. I.A. Sharipova Efficiency of interactive methods of teaching a professionally-oriented English language for students of a technical university.// Theoretical & Applied Science, 2019
7. I.A. Sharipova Didactic games on English language classes as a means of developing professionally significant qualities of a future specialist// Научные горизонты № 1(17) | 2019
8. M. J. Ashirmatova Terminology at the Agrarian University in Russian // International scientific journal Theoretical and practical science // Philadelphia, USA -2021-№ 1.-P. 201-203

9.Ashirmatova M.D. Methodology formation and system of communication ability of university students in the classes of the Russian language [Электронный ресурс]// Мирская наука.-2021.- №10(55) (10.2021).